

Diallel analysis of Al toxicity tolerance in rice

S. Khatiwada, D. Senadhira, and R. S. Zeigler, IRRI; A. L. Carpena and P. G. Fernandez, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines

We studied the genetics of Al toxicity tolerance using a full diallel set of crosses among seven parents with differing degrees of response to Al toxicity. The seven varieties were Moroberekan, IRAT104, and Azucena (tolerant); IR29 and IR43 (moderately tolerant); and IR45 and IR1552 (susceptible).

Relative root length of 14-d-old seedlings, determined by growing seedlings in a normal nutrient solution and nutrient solution with 30 ppm Al, was used to characterize the tolerance of test materials. The experiment was conducted in a glasshouse at the IRRI Phytotron with 29/21 °C day/night temperature and 70% relative humidity. The experimental units consisted of 49 entries (7 × 7 diallel) in randomized complete block design with four replications. Eight seedlings were sampled for each entry in a replication.

Analysis of variance among parents, hybrids, and reciprocals showed highly significant differences among parents and hybrids. Differences between parents and hybrids were not significant. Analysis of variance of the diallels revealed homogeneity of error variance, directional dominance, symmetrical distribution of genes among parents, and that no parent had more dominant genes than did the others.

Covariance-variance graphic analysis showed the adequacy of a simple additive-

Estimates of genetic parameters for relative root length (Al toxicity tolerance) in 7 × 7 diallel cross. IRRI, 1995.

Genetic parameter		Estimate ± SE	
(D) Additive effects		0.0167	± 0.0005 ^a
(H) Dominance effects			
	H1 (due to dominant gene)	0.0041	± 0.0015*
	H2 (due to positive and negative genes)	0.0034	± 0.0013*
	h ² (due to heterozygous loci)	-0.0002	± 0.0009
(F) Gene distribution		0.0028	± 0.0015
(E) Environmental effects		0.0008	± 0.0002*
Proportional values			
(H1/D) ^{1/2}	Mean degree of dominance	0.4954	
(H2/4H1)	Proportion of genes with + or - effects on parents	0.2082	
(KD/KR) ^b	Proportion of dominant and recessive genes in the parents	1.4001	
r ^c	Correlation between (Wr+Vr) and Yr	0.6618	
r ²	Prediction for measurement of completely dominant and recessive parents	0.4380	
(h ² /H2)	Number of gene groups that control tolerance and inhibit dominance	-0.0654	
(h _{ns})	Heritability (narrow sense)	0.8177	
(h _{bs})	Heritability (broad sense)	0.9106	

^a * = significant at P<0.05. ^b KD/KR = [(4DH₁)^{1/2} + FJ]/[(4DH₁)^{1/2} - FJ]. ^c r = correlation between the sum of covariance of an array with nonrecurring parents and variance of an array (Wr + Vr) and parental means (Yr).

dominance model and partial dominance of the trait. It also showed the presence of dominant genes in tolerant varieties and recessive genes in susceptible varieties. Moderately tolerant to tolerant varieties IR43, Azucena, IRAT104, and Moroberekan appeared to contain similar genes for tolerance. Susceptible IR45 possessed most of the recessive genes for tolerance, followed by IR29 and IR1552.

Genetic components of variation and proportional values were estimated (see table). The observed variations were due to additive and dominance effects of genes and the environmental effects. Average degree of dominance was within the range of incomplete dominance. The proportion of dominant and recessive genes in the

parents indicated an excess of dominant genes. Genes with desirable effects (tolerance) were dominant over those with undesirable effects (susceptibility). Only one group of genes with dominance was found to be involved in governing Al toxicity tolerance in rice.

The high narrow-sense heritability (0.82) and the small difference between narrow-sense and broad-sense heritability (0.91) indicated the predominance of additive gene action. Results indicated that in breeding populations, selection for Al toxicity tolerance could be carried out in the early generations. Selection efficiency could be enhanced if done under controlled conditions to reduce environmental effects. ■

Breeding methods

Maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile line IR66707 A

S. B. Pradhan and P. J. Jachuck, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

Since its release in India during 1992, IR64 has become very popular in the irrigated areas of Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh,

Orissa, West Bengal, and Maharashtra. It has high yield, wide adaptability, good plant type, long slender grain, intermediate amylose content, and resistance to major insect pests and diseases.

IRRI scientists developed cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line IR66707A from IR64 by using *Oryza perennis* as a cytoplasmic source. Their intention was to use this CMS line to develop high-yielding, good quality hybrid rice. However, hybrids could

not be developed without effective restorers.

During 1992-93, we made 50 test crosses with IR66707 A using high-yielding varieties adapted to irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions. We found 42 of the varieties to be effective maintainers; one a weak maintainer; five partial restorers; and two, IR21820-38-2 and Mahsuri, to be effective restorers for IR66707 A (Table 1). Unlike in the CMS-wild abortive system,

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers for IR66707 A. CRRI, Cuttack, India. 1992 and 1993 wet seasons.

Male parent	M/R ^a
1992	
ADT34	M
Annada	M
B4143 D-PM-51-4	M
BKS64	M
CR580-17-3	M
CR564-8	M
CR644	M
CRM 35	M
Daya	M
IET10158	M
IET10983	M
IR1846-300-1	M
IR25560-109-3-1-3-2	M
IR1248-242-32	M
Krishna	M
Mizoram 24	M
Mizoram 35	M
Mizoram 41	M
Mizoram 51	M
Mizoram 61	M
Mizoram 62	M
PN56-665	M
Panidhan	M
Pusa 33	M
Rasi	WM
Sarasa	M
Suphala	M
Savitri	M
Tulasi	M
V20	M
Gayatri	PR ^b
Mizoram 39	PR
1993	
ARC13558	M
86441-5. MR. 10-1	M
BR1870-88-11	M
Col. 155	M
C1954-24-2	M
C2757-22-1-1-1	M
IR49689-84-2-1-2	M
IR35366-28-3-1-2-2	M
IR48725-B-B-120-1	M
IR27315-145-1-3-2	M
Katarni	M
Pusa 33-303	M
Vijaya	M
IR49721-127-2-2-1	PR
Raktachandan	PR
Tox 3108-43-3-6	PR
IR21820-38-2	R*1 ^c
Mahsuri	R*2 ^d

^aM = maintainer (spikelet fertility <1%), WM = weak maintainer (spikelet fertility 1-≤25%), PR = partial restorer (spikelet fertility 26-79%), and R = effective restorer (spikelet fertility ≥80%). ^bSpikelet fertility = 76.7%. ^cSpikelet fertility for *1 = 80.2%; *2 = 80.0%.

Table 2. Yield data of two hybrids and check. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Hybrid/check	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield/plant (g)	Standard heterosis (%)
IR66707 A/IR21820-38-2	85	94	36.5	43.1
IR66707 A/Mahsuri	84	95	35.7	40.0
IR36 (check)	90	95	25.5	

the frequency of maintainers in the CMS-*O. perennis* system was very high and the frequency of restorers very low.

IR21820-38-2 and Mahsuri produced hybrids that yielded about 40% more than check IR36 (Table 2.) ■

Biological characteristics of indica-japonica hybrids

Lu Chuan'gen, Gu Fulin, and Zou Jiangshi, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences (JAAS), Nanjing 210014, China

Five indica-japonica hybrids and their parents were tested for their biological characteristics. The experiment was conducted in a 40-m² plot with three replications per variety at the JAAS experimental farm in 1990 and 1991. The hybrids were obtained by crossing indica

lines and japonica wide compatibility lines with the *S-5ⁿ* gene.

The hybrids had grain yields of 7.6-10.6 t/ha and significant heterosis of 13.8-83.1% over the average of their parents. More spikelets per panicle in the hybrids caused the sink capacity to increase by 27.0-70.4% over that of the parents, thus contributing to high grain yields. The panicles per area, however, exhibited no heterosis (Table 1).

The biomass of the hybrids averaged about 18 t/ha. It exceeded that of the parents by 11.5-41.1% and was the biological basis for the hybrids' high grain yield. High leaf

Table 1. Grain yield and yield components in indica-japonica hybrids and their parents.^a Nanjing, China. 1990-91.

Hybrid or parent	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield difference ^b (%)	Panicles (10 ⁶ /ha)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Sink capacity (t/ha)	Biomass (t/ha)
1990								
3037	8.1	abc	38.5	107.5	68.1	24.3	10.1	16.4
3037/02428	9.0	a	24.6	220.0	69.1	22.3	12.0	18.6
	(18.4)		(-21.8)	(66.4)	(-1.2)	(-5.7)	(27.0)	(13.4)
02428	7.1	c	24.4	157.0	72.5	23.0	8.8	16.4
916/02428	8.3	ab	19.6	218.4	68.7	29.2	12.5	19.4
	(46.9)		(-24.3)	(70.2)	(-1.3)	(15.6)	(53.4)	(28.5)
916	4.2	d	27.4	99.6	67.5	27.5	7.5	13.8
916/M2	7.6	bc	20.9	203.5	63.1	28.4	12.1	17.7
	(83.1)		(-8.9)	(39.0)	(-6.6)	(23.2)	(70.4)	(22.9)
M2	4.1	d	18.5	193.3	71.9	18.6	6.7	15.0
1991								
JW28	7.9	cd	19.5	145.0	95.1	28.3	8.0	15.2
3037/JW28	9.5	b	20.7	217.1	79.0	26.8	12.0	19.6
	(13.8)		(-6.5)	(36.9)	(-13.8)	(3.7)	(33.3)	(38.0)
3037	8.8	bc	24.8	172.2	90.4	23.4	10.0	13.2
3037/02428	10.6	a	20.2	241.2	78.1	24.9	12.2	18.2
	(32.5)		(2.0)	(20.5)	(-9.2)	(0.0)	(29.1)	(41.1)
02428	7.2	d	14.8	228.0	84.2	26.4	8.9	12.6
3037/JW12	9.3	b	22.5	193.7	78.8	25.4	11.1	14.1
	(14.1)		(4.7)	(18.0)	(-13.4)	(4.5)	(29.1)	(11.5)
JW12	7.5	d	18.2	156.2	93.9	25.2	7.2	12.1

^aData in parentheses represent the heterosis over the average of the parents. ^bIn the third column, yield differences indicated by different letters are significant at the 1% level.